

A rare case report of brain abscess due to *Nocardia paucivorans* in an immunocompromised patient

Aikaterini Michelaki¹, Maria Kamperogianni¹, Maria Orfanidou¹, Eleni Petrou¹, Aggeliki Tsolaki¹, Vasileios Valadakis², Eleni Papadogeorgaki³, Eleni Vagiakou¹

¹Laboratory of Microbiology, General Hospital "G. Gennimatas", Athens Greece

²Neurosurgery Department, General Hospital "G. Gennimatas", Athens Greece

³Central Laboratories, Hygeia General Hospital, Athens Greece

Summary

Nocardia species are aerobic, Gram positive, filamentous, weakly acid-fast rods that are ubiquitous in the environment. Nocardiosis has been referred to as an opportunistic infection which may be localized or disseminated depending on the host immunity. Diagnosis of *Nocardia* species may be challenging but both early identification and adapted antimicrobial therapy are critical for a favorable outcome. We report a rare case of an immunocompromised patient with *N. paucivorans* brain abscess.

Key words

Nocardia paucivorans, brain abscess, antimicrobial treatment

Corresponding author

Aikaterini Michelaki MD

Bouboulinas 30-32,

Agia Paraskevi, Athens, Greece, 15341

Tel.: +306973629472, email: kmichelaki@yahoo.gr

Introduction

Nocardia species are aerobic, Gram positive, catalase and urease positive, filamentous, right-angled branching rods which present different intensity of acid-fastness. It is ubiquitously found, commonly in the soil and decaying matter.¹ The most frequently identified species responsible for human diseases are *N. asteroides*, *N. farcinica*, *N. brasiliensis* and *N. nova*.² Nocardiosis generally results either post traumatically or after inhalation of the bacteria, leading to pneumonia. It is, also, involved in the process of endocarditis, keratitis and central nervous system (CNS) infections, with the majority of which occurs in occurring in immunocompromised patients.³ The mortality rate of CNS nocardiosis is approximately estimated to be 35%.⁴ Nocardiosis is difficult to diagnose clinically, radiologically and histopathologically. Thus, a definitive diagnosis depends on the isolation and the identification of the specific *Nocardia* species.⁵ In 2000, Yassin et al.⁶ identified a new species of the genus *Nocardia* based on its chemotaxonomic characteristics and molecular data analysis in the sputum of a patient with chronic lung disease which was named *N. paucivorans*. We report here the first case, to our knowledge, of brain abscess in Greece caused by *N. paucivorans*.

Case description

A 70-year-old, nonsmoker female, with a medical history of rheumatoid arthritis treated with methotrexate and corticosteroids, diabetes mellitus and atrial fibrillation, was admitted to our hospital due to reduced level of consciousness in the last 20 hours. Further neurological examination revealed a Glasgow Coma Scale of 11/15, left hemiparesis, isocoria and pupils reacting to light. No fever had been noticed in the past month prior to admission. The white blood cells (WBC) count was 29.900 cells/ μ L (87,20% neutrophils) and C-Reactive Protein (CRP) was 46,4 mg/L. A brain CT scan (Figure 1) showed a right frontal cystic lesion with abundant surrounding edema and associated mass effect while a CT scan of the chest and abdomen area did not show any abnormalities. The patient underwent a mini craniotomy, evacuation of the purulent collection, and resection of the abscess wall. During the operation samples from the abscess were collected and sent for histopathological and microbiological investigation. Empiric antibiotic therapy consisting of Ceftriaxone (2gr \times 2), Vancomycin (1gr \times 2), and Metronidazole (500mg \times 3), was initiated intravenously. The preliminary histopathological findings were indicative of a brain abscess. In the microbiological laboratory, Gram stain

of the pus showed numerous neutrophils but no microorganisms. The specimen was inoculated in Thio-glycolate broth, MacConkey, Sabouraud and Blood agar (bioMérieux, France) and incubated at 37° C in an aerobic atmosphere, plus in Chocolate agar (bioMérieux, France) which was incubated at 37° C in an atmosphere enriched with 5% CO₂. However, no growth was observed after four days of incubation. On the fifth day small, whitish and chalky colonies appeared on blood and chocolate agar penetrating the agar (Figure 2). Gram stain of the culture showed Gram positive branching, beaded, filamentous rods. This finding led to the performance of modified Ziehl-Nielsen stain which revealed a partially and weakly acid-fast bacteria (Figure 3). All the above raised the suspicion of *Nocardia* spp. as the possible pathogen. Finally, *N. paucivorans* was identified by Matrix Assisted Laser Desorption Ionization Time-of-Flight mass spectrometry (MALDI-TOF, VITEK MS, bioMérieux, France). The susceptibility and the Minimum Inhibitory Concentrations (MICs) of trimethoprim-sulfamethoxazole, linezolid, ceftriaxone and ciprofloxacin were determined by the use of gradient antibiotic strips (E-test, bioMérieux, France) on Mueller Hinton Agar with 5% Sheep Blood. After 48 hours of incubation, the results were reported and interpreted as susceptible, intermediate or resistant according to the breakpoints recommended by the CLSI M62.¹¹ *N. paucivorans* was susceptible *in vitro* to trimethoprim-sulfamethoxazole (0,125 μ g/mL), linezolid (0,5 μ g/mL), ceftriaxone (0,125 μ g/mL) and ciprofloxacin (0,25 μ g/mL). Therefore, the antimicrobial therapy was modified accordingly, to trimethoprim-sulfamethoxazole, linezolid and ceftriaxone. Unfortunately, two weeks after diagnosis and with her condition worsening, the patient deceased because of the nocardiosis.

Discussion

Nocardia spp. are found extensively worldwide and belong to the Nocardiaceae family. The first description of *Nocardia* was reported in 1888 by the veterinarian Edmond Nocard in bovine disease.⁷ *Nocardia* spp. cause chronic, progressive infections that may be localized or disseminated. The majority of the above infections occur in immunocompromised patients but infections among immunocompetent patients have also been reported, with pulmonary and cutaneous nocardiosis being the most frequent clinical presentations. The CNS is the most common site involved in disseminated nocardiosis and is often accompanied by pulmonary disease. However, isolated CNS nocardiosis may also occur, with brain abscess being the most prevalent clinical manifestation of CNS infection.⁸

Figure 1

Figure 2

Figure 3

N. paucivorans was firstly identified in 2000, in the sputum of a patient with chronic lung disease.⁶ Since then, in the world medical literature, to our knowledge, 50 cases of *N. paucivorans* infections have been published and brain abscesses have been reported in 17 of 50 cases.⁹

Diagnosis of nocardiosis may be missed by laboratories firstly due to the slow growth of *Nocardia* species in culture. Colonies of *Nocardia* normally appear after 2-14 days in culture media and the prolonged incubation of the plates, for up to two weeks, is recommended. Secondly, another barrier to *Nocardia* spp.

conclusive and quick identification is their similarity to *Actinomyces* species on Gram stain. However, *Actinomyces* are distinctively not acid-fast and can also grow under anaerobic conditions. As a result, many laboratories fail to identify *Nocardia* which leads to nocardiosis being an underdiagnosed disease. MALDI-TOF and gene sequence analysis using 16s ribosomal RNA are currently the most commonly used methods of identifying *Nocardia* spp. but cannot be always used routinely as these diagnostic tools are unavailable in most microbiology laboratories.¹⁰ Therefore, the accurate and prompt diagnosis of nocardiosis can be challenging.

In spite of its *in vitro* antimicrobial susceptibility, broth microdilution is the recommended method by the CLSI.¹¹ The E-test is a suitable alternative method for *Nocardia* susceptibility testing. Different studies using CLSI interpretive criteria reported an agreement of >90% between E-tests and broth microdilution and additionally noted that resistance is species dependent. These variances in susceptibility testing suggest that the identification of *Nocardia* organisms at a species level is essential. Therefore, the determination of MICs

values is essential for advanced therapeutic decisions.^{12,13}

As for the treatment options, trimethoprim-sulfamethoxazole is considered to be the first-line drug for nocardiosis although some *Nocardia* species such as *N. nova* and *N. farcinica* have occasionally been found to be resistant. Nevertheless, it still remains the agent of choice, particularly in patients with cerebral abscesses due to its good CNS penetration. Combination therapy with trimethoprim-sulfamethoxazole and other drugs as ceftriaxone, carbapenems and linezolid has successfully been used in severe nocardiosis.^{13,14}

In conclusion, brain abscess caused by *N. paucivorans* is a rare disease. However, *Nocardia* spp. have a specific tropism for the CNS and should always be included in the differential diagnosis, particularly in immunocompromised patients. Thus, the timely detection of the specific *Nocardia* spp. and the initiation of an appropriate treatment regime is most likely to lead to a successful clinical outcome.

Declaration of interest

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

Περίληψη

Περιγραφή σπάνιας περίπτωσης εγκεφαλικού αποστήματος από *Nocardia paucivorans* σε ανοσοκατασταλαμένο ασθενή

Αικατερίνη Μιχελάκη¹, Μαρία Καμπερογιάννη¹, Μαρία Ορφανίδου¹, Ελένη Πέτρου¹
Αγγελική Τσολάκη¹, Βασίλειος Βαλαδάκης², Ελένη Παπαδογεωργάκη³, Ελένη Βαγιάκου¹

¹Μικροβιολογικό εργαστήριο, Γενικό Νοσοκομείο Αθηνών "Γ. Γεννηματάς"

²Νευροχειρουργική Κλινική, Γενικό Νοσοκομείο Αθηνών "Γ. Γεννηματάς"

³Κεντρικά Εργαστήρια, Νοσοκομείο "Υγεία", Αθήνα

Τα είδη *Nocardia* είναι αερόβια, Gram θετικά, ασθενώς οξεάντοχα βακτηρίδια τα οποία βρίσκονται σε αφθονία στο περιβάλλον. Η νοκαρδίωση αναφέρεται κυρίως ως μια ευκαιριακή λοίμωξη που ανάλογα με την ανοσιακή κατάσταση του ασθενούς μπορεί να είναι τοπική ή συστηματική. Η διάγνωση της *Nocardia* spp. αποτελεί πρόκληση για το μικροβιολογικό εργαστήριο καθώς η έγκαιρη ταυτοποίηση και η κατάλληλη αντιμικροβιακή θεραπεία είναι σημαντικά για μια επιτυχή έκβαση. Παρουσιάζεται μια σπάνια περίπτωση εγκεφαλικού αποστήματος από *N. paucivorans* σε ανοσοκατασταλαμένο ασθενή.

Λέξεις κλειδιά

Nocardia paucivorans, εγκεφαλικό απόστημα, αντιμικροβιακή θεραπεία

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